

3-Hydroxy-2-Methyl-1,4-Naphthoquinone Monoxime : A New Sensitive Reagent for the Determination of Iron(II) and Cobalt(II)

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3-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone monoxime is suggested for the estimation of 21.5-114.0 μg iron(II) and 3.5-41.5 μg cobalt(II) over the pH range 4.8-7.0 and 5.0-7.5, respectively. The iron(II) and cobalt(II) complexes possess maximum absorption at 460 nm and 430 nm, respectively with the molar absorptivities of 1.28×10^4 and $3.24 \times 10^4 \text{ l. cm}^{-1} \cdot \text{mole}^{-1}$. The determinations have been carried out in 50% ethanol. The limits of tolerance of foreign ions have been studied.

A number of spectrophotometric reagents are known for the determination of iron and cobalt but very few are well suited for the purpose. Reagents known for ferric iron suffer from the disadvantage that they cannot be used in presence of appreciable quantities of pyrophosphate or fluoride ions which form stable complexes with ferric iron in acidic medium. In such cases reagents which react with ferrous iron work better since ferrous iron either does not form such complexes or are less stable. Oximidobenzotetronic acid¹, violuric acid², 8-hydroxyquinoline^{3,4} and acetylacetone^{5,6} have been suggested for the determination of iron, but controlled parameters and interference due to several ions do not permit any advantage over the widely used reagents. Another useful reagent for iron(II) is 8-hydroxyquinoline-carboxylic acid in which large amounts of copper, nickel, cobalt, aluminium, zinc and manganese are tolerated. However, the reagent lacks sensitivity and the complex has to be extracted in a mixture of pyridine and chloroform. Catechol violet⁷ is a sensitive reagent for iron but copper, molybdenum, magnesium, antimony and phosphate interfere in the determination.

Phenanthrenequinone monoxime⁸, dithioamide⁹, 2,2'-dipyridylketoxime¹⁰, 3-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyltriazine¹¹, violuric acid¹², quinoxaline-2,3-dithiol¹³, acetone hydrochloric acid¹⁴ and phenanthrenequinone mono-semicarbazone¹⁵ have been introduced as sensitive and selective reagents for the microdetermination of cobalt. Thiocyanate method¹⁶, when used in aqueous acetone medium, is subject to many limitations. A large amount of reagent is necessary for complete colour development and iron(III), chromium, copper, uranium, bismuth and nickel interfere. Alkaline earth metals give precipitates. The reagent does not form intensely coloured complex and extraction into organic solvents is necessary to concentrate the coloured product. Many elements interfere and hence the method has limited application. The regulation of acidity is

of great importance in this procedure, especially so far as the suppression of the interference of iron is concerned. *o*-Nitrosocresol^{17,18} is a sensitive reagent for cobalt and the method has advantages over the nitroso-R-salt method when the amount of cobalt to be determined is very small. The reagent is not obtainable in the solid form, its solution must be prepared by the analyst and it is not very stable. Special precautions are to be taken to prevent the interference of traces of iron in the procedure. The cobalt complex absorbs in the ultraviolet region ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 360 \text{ nm}$).

The present method using 3-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone monoxime (HMNQM) compares favourably with other methods known for the determination of iron(II) and cobalt(II). Extraction is not required since the complexes are soluble in alcoholic medium. The method is simple and the colour remains stable for a long time. A comparison of the sensitivity of HMNQM with other well known reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of iron and cobalt is made in Table 1.

Experimental

Reagents and equipment : 3-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (Phthiocol) was prepared by the method of Fieser¹⁹. 1 g of phthiocol was dissolved in about 20 ml of ethanol and an aqueous solution containing 1.5 g of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and an equal amount of anhydrous sodium acetate was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 2 hr, filtered, cooled in ice and the oxime was precipitated by adding water to it. The oxime thus obtained was recrystallised from ethanol (m.p. 200-204°).

Stock solution of iron(II) was prepared by dissolving reagent grade ferrous ammonium sulphate in double distilled water in presence of a few drops of sulphuric acid. Cobalt(II) solution was prepared by dissolving cobaltous sulphate heptahydrate. Both

TABLE 1—SENSITIVITIES OF VARIOUS REAGENTS FOR Fe(II) and Co(II)

Reagent	Sensitivity $\mu\text{g Fe/cm}^2$	Reagent	Sensitivity $\mu\text{g Co/cm}^2$
Thiocyanate + acetone	0.004/480 nm	Nitroso-R-salt	0.0019/420 nm 0.0042/520 nm
1,10-Phenanthroline	0.005/508 nm	Thiocyanate	0.055/625 nm 0.009/310 nm
8-Quinoline-carboxylic acid	0.24/550 nm	2,2'-Dipyridylketoxime	0.0029/388 nm
Acetylacetone	0.173/435 nm	2,3-Quinoxaline- dithiol	0.0016/505 nm 0.0064/598 nm 0.0379/650 nm
Catechol violet	0.002/610 nm	Hydrochloric acid	0.200/625 nm
3-Hydroxy-1,3- diphenyltriazine	0.0056/418 nm	Dithiooxamide	0.0046/400 nm
Thiocyanate	0.008/480 nm	3-Hydroxy-1,3- diphenyltriazine	0.0039/420 nm
Nitroso-R-salt	0.0023/720 nm 0.007/620 nm	2-Nitroso-1- naphthol/CHCl ₃	0.0042/530 nm
2,6-Diacetylpyridine dioxime	0.0048/485 nm	Phenanthrene- quinone mono- semicarbazone	0.0049/470 nm
3-Hydroxy-2-methyl- 1,4-naphthoquinone monoxime (HMNQM) (present method)	0.0043/460 nm	HMNQM (present method)	0.0018/430 nm

the solutions were standardised gravimetrically. Test solutions, as required, were prepared by further dilutions.

The pH of the solutions, adjusted with the help of acetate buffers using NaOH for higher values, was measured with an ECIL expanded scale pH meter, pH821A. All absorbance measurements were carried out with Unicam spectrophotometer, model SP 600 using 1.00 cm absorption cells.

Recommended procedure :

To a sample solution containing 21.5-114 μg of iron(II) or 3.5-41.5 μg of cobalt(II) is added 1 ml of 1×10^{-2} M ethanolic solution of the reagent for Fe(II) or 0.5 ml of 1×10^{-2} M for cobalt(II) and the pH is adjusted to 4.8-7.0 for iron(II) and 5.0-7.5 for cobalt(II). Alcohol is added and the mixture is diluted to 25 ml keeping ethanol concentration around 50% to obtain a homogeneous solution. The absorbance is measured at 460 nm for iron(II) and 430 nm for cobalt(II) using a corresponding reagent blank. The amount of iron or cobalt in the sample is calculated from a calibration graph prepared with known quantities of the respective metal.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra and effect of pH : The absorption spectra of iron(II) and cobalt(II) complexes of HMNQM against the corresponding reagent blanks are given in Fig. 1, which show that the brown coloured iron(II) and yellow coloured cobalt(II) complexes absorb maximally at 460 and 430 nm, respectively. The absorbances of iron(II) and cobalt(II) complexes displayed a constancy in the pH range of 4.8-7.0 and 5.0-7.5, respectively.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of reagent and its complexes.

- I. Iron(II) complex vs reagent.
- II. Cobalt(II) complex vs reagent.
- III. Reagent vs 50% ethanol.

Subsequent studies were carried out at pH 5.8 and 6.0, respectively.

Effect of reagent concentration : It was observed that full colour development was obtained when 4-fold molar excess of reagent was present in case of iron(II) and 6-fold in case of cobalt(II) (Fig. 2). However, the concentration of the reagent in subsequent studies was maintained at 10 times that of the metal in either of the cases.

Fig. 2. Composition by mole ratio method.
I. Iron(II) complex.
II. Cobalt(II) complex.

Beer's law, optimum range and sensitivity of the reaction: The brown coloured iron(II) complex follows Beer's law up to 5.8 ppm of iron(II). The optimum range of concentration of iron for accurate determination, as deduced from Ringbom plot (Fig. 3) was found to be 0.86-4.6 ppm. The sensitivity was found to be $0.0043 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for $\log I_0/I=0.001$ with molar absorptivity of $1.28 \times 10^4 \text{ l.cm}^{-1}.\text{mole}^{-1}$ at 460 nm.

Fig. 3. I. Ringbom plot for Fe(II)-HMNQM complex.
II. Ringbom plot for Co(II)-HMNQM complex.

The yellow complex of Co(II)-HMNQM obeys Beer's law up to 1.8 ppm of Co(II). As deduced from Ringbom plot (Fig. 3), the optimum range for the determination is 0.14-1.7 ppm of Co(II) with a molar absorptivity of $3.24 \times 10^4 \text{ l.cm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$ at 430 nm and the sensitivity according to Sandell's definition is $0.0018 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ for an absorbance of 0.001.

Precision of the method: Measured under optimum conditions, the solutions containing 2.23 ppm of iron(II) gave absorbance readings with an average relative deviation of 0.38% and standard deviation of 0.0027. Eight samples each containing

1.12 ppm of cobalt(II) gave an average relative deviation of 0.35% and standard deviation of 0.003.

Stoichiometry of the complexes: The molar composition of iron(II) and cobalt(II) chelates of HMNQM was determined by mole ratio²⁰ (Fig. 2) and Job's method of continuous variations^{21,22} (Fig. 4). The two methods indicated the formation of 1 : 3 (metal : ligand) complex in either of the cases.

Fig. 4. Composition by Job's method.

I. Iron(II) complex ; total molarity = $1.92 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$.
II. Cobalt(II) complex ; total molarity = $9.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$.

Interference due to foreign ions: The effect of foreign ions was studied in the determination of 2.23 ppm of iron(II) and the concentration of various ions which did not cause any interference are given in Table 2. Nickel(II), cobalt(II) and

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF Fe(II) IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS

Foreign ion	Amount tolerated (ppm)	Foreign ion	Amount tolerated (ppm)
Chloride	300	Magnesium(II)	200
Bromide	300	Aluminium(III)	125
Iodide	300	Zinc(II) ¹	60
Fluoride	300	Cadmium(II)	50
Nitrite	100	Cobalt(II)	5
Nitrate	200	Mercury(II)	50
Thiosulphate	400	Copper(II) ²	50
Thiourea	400	Manganese(II)	50
Citrate	50	Chromium(III) ¹	30
Tartrate	400	Tin(II) ¹	30
Sulphite	300	Uranium(VI) ³	40
Thiocyanate	400	Ruthenium(III)	2
Phosphate	350	Rhodium(III)	2
Oxalate	100	Palladium(II) ⁴	4
Strontium(II)	50	Osmium(VIII) ⁵	3
Barium(II)	100	Iridium(III)	4
Calcium(II)	100	Platinum(IV)	4
		Tungsten(VI)	50

1—Masked with tartrate; 2—masked with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-} + \text{I}^-$; 3—masked with PO_4^{3-} ; 4—masked with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$; 5—masked with SCN^- .

cyanide interfere seriously. The limits of tolerance of various ions in the determination of 1.12 ppm of

cobalt(II) are incorporated in Table 3. Serious interferences were caused due to nickel(II) and cyanide.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF COBALT(II) IN PRESENCE OF FOREIGN IONS

Foreign ion	Amount tolerated (ppm)	Foreign ion	Amount tolerated (ppm)
Chloride	200	Zinc(II)	70
Bromide	200	Cadmium(II)	70
Nitrate	200	Mercury(II)	30
Nitrite	100	Vanadium(IV) ²	50
Phosphate	300	Chromium(III) ³	50
Oxalate	100	Tin(II) ³	50
Fluoride	400	Arsenic(III)	20
Thiocyanate	400	Silver(I) ⁴	10
Sulphate	200	Thorium(IV) ⁵	20
Citrate	200	Magnesium(II)	50
Tartrate	150	Uranyl(II)	100
Thiourea	150	Palladium(II) ⁶	4
Thiosulphate	200	Osmium(VIII) ⁶	4
Iodide	150	Platinum(IV)	5
Sulphite	150	Iridium(III)	4
Calcium(II)	80	Ruthenium(III)	4
Barium(II)	50	Rhodium(III)	3
Aluminium(III)	70	Tungsten(VI)	40
Iron(II)	35	Copper(II) ¹	30
Manganese	70		

1—Masked with $S_2O_3^{2-} + I^-$; 2—masked with fluoride; 3—masked with tartrate; 4—masked with chloride; 5—masked with thiosulphate; 6—masked with thiocyanate.

Practical applications :

Determination of iron in BCS 241/1 alloy steel : The iron content was determined in BCS 241/1 alloy steel. The solution of the alloy was prepared by the method of Singh *et al*²³. 1 ml of 10% hydroxylamine hydrochloride solution was added to ensure that all the iron is present as iron(II). The certified composition of the alloy is Fe=70.91, C=0.84, Ni=0.15, Cu=0.08, V=1.59, Sn=0.025, Co=5.7, Mn=0.27, S=0.025, Cr=5.35, Mo=0.53, Si=0.21, P=0.024%. Triplicate analysis of the sample gave 71.16% iron with a standard deviation of 0.012.

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